

Adulteration of the Record of Samaritan History

by

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In my articles *Samaritan History, Fiction, and Bad Fantasy* and *Roman Policy towards Samaritans in the Second Century A.D.*, it was shown that about seven pericopes in the book by Abu 'l-Fateh,² were not what came from the hand of the author. It was argued that the original histories had been replaced by fictionalised history with some pure invention. All seven or so pericopes of the booklet now attached to the end of the Arabic Joshua book were used, but with more or less revised wording and sometimes expanded. At the same time it was argued, mainly in the article *Samaritan History*, that the damage to the work went further than that. Some of the damage was identified, but for the purpose of those two articles, there was no need to try for completeness. What follows is a first attempt at identifying the extent of adulteration of the work of A.F., which parts have been altered and how badly. Tracing evidence of deliberate textual alteration must be done cautiously, and this first time round only really obvious passages will be treated. It is better to have more basic references or basic pieces of information (points de repère) that are all certain than to have more examples with a few wrong identifications. This is the only way that the methods used by the reviser or more accurately falsifier can be found with confidence in the details.

Content of the book commonly attributed to A.F.

We start with the long set of pericopes about Bāba Rabba. The falsifier makes him a leader fighting against persecution, while calling him a king in the piece about the emperor Philip, and quoting the detailed description of his administration near the start. It has been established that the accounts of persecution under Commodus, Septimius Severus, and someone called Alexander are transfers of conditions at some times under the rule of Christian Rome. Alexander is a generic Roman emperor, so there is no point to trying to identify who is behind the name. The accounts have been moved, but they are true for all that. Not all the onslaughts were directly physical. There was use of economics, social disruption, and social disadvantage to try to make all Samaritans disappear. The weapons used against the religion were built by legislation. There was genocidal intent. If children of Samaritans were not Samaritans themselves, this was just as effective as mass murder and a lot cheaper. There was, however, a lot of mass murder by forcing the Samaritans in Samaria to revolt to survive. In Antioch there was a massacre, but in general economics and intolerable social disadvantage

¹ **The author has no connection with the State of Israel.**

² This transcription represents the actual pronunciation.

were the weapon in the diaspora. The state obeyed the Christian Church. Christianity needed to wipe out all record of Samaritan religion. The details of all this are in my book of 2024 and there is no need to repeat them in an article.

The reasons given for these supposed persecutions are so bad that the falsity of the stories is confirmed. Commodus is said to have been annoyed on hearing about a philosophical debate. The falsifier can't think of anything even this weak to explain the supposed actions of the rest of the emperors named. He did not expect the intended readers to notice anything wrong.

One explanation of why the falsifier put the stories about persecutions under Pagan Rome where he did is that he did not know much. Legislation and economics and social structure were beyond his ken. Another explanation might be that he did not know enough about the real wars to say enough over enough pages for what he wanted. This second answer does not seem to be satisfactory. A.F. would not have left these out. In what survives of his work, Constantios II and Theodosios II are named. They were not connected with the wars, but the surviving mention of their names shows that the original work as it left the hand of the author had factual detail. The wars might not have been at times that suited the falsifier. He wanted a set of stories about a combined ruler and resistance leader. No matter if the two were incompatible with each other: he could not visualise readers more competent than himself. He wanted to use a known name. No matter how he cooked the records, he could not put the start of his activity more than ninety years too late or put the end of his activity more than a hundred and fifty years too late, or make him active at the age of 130 or more.

There are some low-quality fantastic stories about Bāba's exploits against Romans ruling from Constantinople interpolated into the work of A.F. These stories are enough on their own to justify my assessment of the level of the falsifier along with the level of the readers aimed at. The story about the worthy Roman official Girmon is connected with Bāba in its first version, in the attachment to the Arabic Joshua book. His father Nātānel is named. This gives Bāba an impossible date. That degree of falsification turned out to be unsustainable. In the second version of the story about Girmon, interpolated into the work of A.F., the emperor Constantios is named. This is Constantios II, who reigned from 337 till 361. (The name is given as Ṭī'os. The correct form is in two of the St. Petersburg Fragments). If Bāba had been born when the falsifier said in the pericope before the story about Girmon in both versions, he would have been 130 by the first years of the reign of this emperor, so there is a bad contradiction. The pericope connecting Girmon with Bāba must have been written before the falsifier decided on something more ambitious, revising and shortening the whole of the work of A.F. He put the right name of the emperor at the time of Girmon back in in the second version. He gave the right name of the High Priest, Iqbon. He had decided to try to get his work taken seriously. Bāba was taken out of the story and moved back two centuries to the third century in the version of the stories interpolated into the work of A.F. This was still the wrong date. There is a set of pericopes about persecution under two named emperors and a few unnamed ones under a single generic name, something vague about Gordian, and a mention of Philip in a setting a hundred years too late. Bāba's birth is put in the time of the unidentifiable emperors and before Gordian. The pericope about Girmon, now with no connection with Bāba, is still attached to these pericopes by inertia. All these pericopes were interpolated into the work of A.F. in one go.

The pericope about Hadrian fused with Vespasian might have been written before the pericopes about Commodus, Septimius Severus, a lot of undifferentiated emperors, Gordian, and Philip. This seems to be the only explanation for the fictional stories about him attacking Samaritans, which contradict the other parts. Be that as it may, this pericope replaced all mention of anything between Sejanus and Hadrian, including both Jewish insurrections. No reason is given for Hadrian to have gone to Jerusalem or destroyed the Jerusalem temple wearing his Vespasian hat. A.F. would have known better.

The three long pericopes about Dositheos and his immediate followers, then the nefarious Simon invented by the Christian Church, then the Dosithean factions, are in the wrong place. I went into this in my article *The Second Recension of the Work of Abu 'l-Fateh*. The conclusion there was that the first and third of these had been cut out but restored by someone else later on, but in a provisional place that anyone could see was not right, after Constantios II, who reigned from 337 to 361. I suggested that they could not be put in the right place because they had been altered while floating round as a separate pamphlet, and could not be put back without some editorial work, which the restorer was reluctant to do and left for someone more expert some time later on. Modern authors defeated this plan and thought the three pericopes were set just after Bāba or during his time. Aside from not being able to read, they might have been misled by a gloss in the Tūlāda saying Dositheos appeared in the time of Bāba. I now think this proposal that there was a restorer might be an unnecessary complication. I now think the falsifier might have changed his mind and taken the set of three pericopes out to relieve the reader and then changed his mind again and put them back, but in the wrong place. The falsifier could have made up the pericope about Simon and put it between the other two, to relieve the reader of too much information in one go. In my article I showed how the last part of the first pericope had been altered in the process of attaching the new second pericope, about Simon; and how the start of the third pericope, about the Dosithean factions, needs to be read as attached to the last sentences of what is now the first pericope.

In the same article I suggested that the long detailed piece of information on Bāba's administration was put back at the same time as the three pericopes. There is an editorial note saying it is taken from the Tūlāda, which is given the wrong name. I now think this proposal to be an unnecessary complication. The editorial voice is probably the falsifier. There is still the question of why he did not copy from the work of A.F. Well, he might have. If he had done that he still would have fibbed about where he copied it from when he put it back. He might have got the Tūlāda mixed up with the Chain of High Priests because he never looked.

After the information about the Dosithean factions there is nothing, nothing at all, of the standard of the work of A.F. till the destruction of the Samaritan sanctuary by the emperor Zēnōn in 484 A.D. There is no solid historical record for the years between the end of the reign of Constantios II in 361 and the destruction of the sanctuary in 484. The single mention of Constantios II is the only piece of history after the end of the reign of Philip in 249. Even this bit is dubious in its present form. There is suspicious detail about subterfuges to hide the baby that is not what would have been preserved. After Constantios II there are only stories about individuals, some that might be rewriting of events, some that are completely made up. These are different to the accounts of debates and disputes recorded by A.F. (What is said about Alexander in the book as we have it is not an exception. The first part of this comes from the

set of seven or so supposedly entertaining stories in the pamphlet attached at the end of the Arabic Joshua book. The rest can be attributed to the same author).

Before assessing the extent of damage over the whole book, a survey of the content of the book as it stands for the centuries between Bāba (put at the wrong time) and Muhammad.

We start with a mention of the emperor Philip. Stenhouse p. 202. This emperor reigned from 244 to 249. It says here that he reigned from Constantinople. The falsifier depicts a Christian city. He had no sense of historical time. Neither did his intended readers. Ben-Ḥayyim took this story seriously as a historical document that could be used to date Bāba. He took no notice of the mention of the emperor Philip. Many others have used the same technique.

After all the stories about Bāba there is a stupid story about a High Priest called Iqbon and his daughter. Stenhouse p. 206. I described this story in my article *Samaritan History, Fiction, and Bad Fantasy*, pp. 2 bottom to 3 top. A.F. did not write rubbish like this.

After this comes the emperor Decius. Stenhouse p. 208. This emperor reigned from 249 to 251. It says at length that he persecuted Samaritans. He did persecute Christians, for reasons that would not have been relevant to Samaritans. This pericope is pure fiction.

Then comes the emperor Constantios II and the story about the worthy Roman official Girmon. Stenhouse p. 209. This emperor reigned from 337 to 361. The story can be accepted as true, though the form has been embellished. This author says he was next after Decius. He has dropped 86 years. An aside. Montgomery says Girmon is called a qasīs and says this means an ecclesiastical dignitary or a governor. He thinks this must be a bishop of Neapolis called Germanos. There is no word qasīs. There is a word qissīs. It means a Christian priest or minister at any level at all. It does not mean a governor. This word quoted by Montgomery is not in the text, and neither is any related word. Girmon is called a high-ranking official, literally a representative, meaning a representative of the emperor. Germanos was not a common name, but was not rare either. Montgomery is commonly quoted on this, because no-one has looked at what is written on the page. Arrogance like this is normal in writing on the Samaritans.

After this comes the pericope about Dositheos. Stenhouse p. 211. Then the pericope about Simon, then the pericope about the Dosithean factions.

After the pericope about the Dosithean factions comes a story about the daughter of a High Priest called Elāazar. Stenhouse p. 230. There is a mention of the emperor Oualēs (Valens),³ who ruled from 364 to 378 A.D. The story is about how a wicked guardian tries to get hold of the daughter's assets, and she successfully appeals to the emperor. The author is aiming at the usual simple-minded readers. He says the daughter accosted the emperor as he was travelling nearby. No legal system would require the emperor's personal attention to everything. A case like the one described would be handled by a local court. If something did need the emperor's personal attention, it would be passed on by a court or the civil administration. There would have been a mechanism for appealing to the emperor. It would not have been done by accosting him as he was travelling. There might or might not have been

³ The correct form is وليس Wāles, stressed on the first syllable.

such a case. If there was, it did not get resolved in the way described in this story. Still no mention of the kinds of events normally recorded by A.F.

Next entry. Stenhouse p. 232. Right after the story just described. A story about a High Priest called Iqbon. No emperor is mentioned. A.F. would not have been this careless about the date. An informant is mentioned. What is said to be his name seems to be the Greek word for an official informant, sykophantēs. See Montgomery, p. 108. The author of the fiction thinks the word is someone's name, or pretends he thinks that. There is a long story about the High Priest's initiative in putting up a big synagogue on Mt. Gerizim. The size is given as 44 by 77 and seven-eighths cubits, or just under 66 feet by just under 117 feet. So far this might be fact. It might come from the plan lodged for official approval. The rest is fiction. The author thinks this is very big. It is not. He says there had never been a big synagogue building on the Mountain since the end of the Time of Favour. This is obviously a wrong assumption or a brazen invention. He says the doorway was 8 cubits wide by 15 cubits high, or just under 12 by 22½ feet. The width is a plausible size for the entrance to a porch with an open front, but the height is not right. The width is unlikely to be right for a pair of doors and the height comes from the author's undisciplined imagination. The author says the doors had come from the temple in Jerusalem, and Hadrian had taken them to Mt. Gerizim and used them in the temple he put up there. The author fuses Hadrian with Vespasian. He says Hadrian's temple was on Mt. Gerizim, when it was on the lower peak. The fusion of Hadrian with Vespasian is in the extant form of the pericope about Hadrian. So is the story about the doors from the Jerusalem temple being put on the Pagan temple. In the extant form of the pericope about Hadrian the two peaks are distinguished and it is made clear where the Pagan temple was. The author of this story about building a synagogue needed to say the temple of Zeus had been on Mt. Gerizim, that is, on the higher sacred peak, because he needed a story that the gates had been hidden there for centuries. He had to make it the sacred peak so he could make up a story that the hiding-place had been known to each High Priest and no-one else. He contradicted what he had written in the pericope about Hadrian, but the readers intended would never notice. At the same time he needed to dodge the question of how the massive and massively heavy doors were moved from one peak to the other. This author says the Greek word quoted at the start of this paragraph, which he says was someone's name, was inscribed on the doors of the synagogue. He does not explain why. He might have deliberately changed a record that official certification that the building was Samaritan property and had been put up with official permission was put on the front of a big synagogue built at this time. If so, he left out the explanation that certification was needed as part of new legislation against Samaritans. A.F. did not write fiction, even if he recorded some events in traditional legendary form. He did not write for simple-minded readers.

Next entry. Stenhouse p. 238. A mention of the emperor Theodosios II, who reigned from 408 to 450. ⁴ It says all Samaritans were expelled from Neapolis by order of the emperor. This looks like a true record, unchanged by the falsifier.

Next entry. Stenhouse same page. Set during the reign of the emperor Markianos, who reigned from 450 to 457. The Christians tried to get possession of the tombs of Elāazar, Itāmar,

⁴ Correct form تديوس Tēdi'os, stressed on the second syllable.

and Fīnāas. The author says they were High Priests. Itāmar was not, and the difference between him and Fīnāas in this respect is important. A.F. would not have made a bad mistake like that. The governor of Palestine decided to have possession decided by a contest between two champions. The Christians had an unnaturally powerful dog as well as a champion. It is not explained how this was allowed. The Samaritan champion won. This is written for the simple-minded. It can be believed that the Christians tried to steal the religious sites owned by the Samaritans, and they petitioned the governor to enforce their property rights.

Next entry. Stenhouse p. 239. The persecutions under the emperor Zēnōn, who reigned from 474 to 491, with an interruption of one year. The destruction of the sanctuary. This pericope is treated in my book of 2024, pp. 110 to 113. It seems to have been preserved as A.F. wrote it but with embellishment. There is a lot of information but careful reading is needed. The falsifier did not understand a lot.

I have not left much out. Look how little is supposed to have happened over the centuries of Roman rule. What is said to have happened is mostly inconsequential or has been fictionalised or made up altogether. After the notice of Antoninus Pius (probably fused with Marcus Aurelius) there is overwhelmingly only fairy floss, not history. Even the notice of Antoninus is vague and inferior. There is some trace of real events behind the fiction in a few places. There are a few very short snippets of real information. The two long pericopes about Dositheos and the Dosithean factions are solid information, though in the wrong place.

Next entry. Stenhouse p. 242. It is said that after Zēnōn there was no social order. There were gangs of bandits everywhere. I think what that means is that the falsifier couldn't be bothered rewriting any more, accounts of wars would not be entertaining, and the cost of copying had to be kept down.

After this comes the mention of Muhammad. Stenhouse p. 242. There is fact, but some fiction mixed in. I have not seen the name of the Samaritan delegate, Yirmīya, anywhere else in a Samaritan writing.⁵ It is probably accurate because it is not what would have been made up. There is not much detail, however. The names of Muhammad's officials are accurate. The story about the three astrologers looks like a fictionalised version of the fact that Samaritans survived wherever Christian rule ended, Jews benefited, and Christians with the wrong label benefited. There were more of the last in Egypt than Palestine.

Then comes a statement by A.F. speaking in the first person on chronology equivalent to the one at the start of the book, but bringing it up to the time of Muhammad. Stenhouse p. 249. Like the first one, it has been altered by the falsifier so as to drop two years at the time of the Flood. See my article *Restoring the Traditional Linkage*, pp. 2 and 3. The alteration in both places is a copy of what he did himself in the Arabic Joshua book years before. The words addressed to the reader trying to push acceptance are in the same tone. The list of High Priests has been interpolated by the falsifier with a note saying the years that Bāba Rabba officiated should not be counted in adding up lengths of time because he officiated while his father was alive. This is a contradiction of the Tūlāda. It is contrary to how counting is actually done.

⁵ Wrongly written אמריא but the correction אמריא is obvious. I think the falsifier got it wrong because he did not recognise the name.

Then the real A.F. returns to the narrative. Stenhouse top of p. 249. He brings the book to an end with a general observation on Muhammad's favourable relations with the Samaritans. **After that the falsifier, speaking in the first person, says "This is what I found in this history"**. (Not in Vilmar's ed. but belonging after 180:12. Stenhouse bottom of p. 249). This is obviously not A.F. speaking. **The words mean the falsifier made his own edition of the whole book written by A.F. and here it is for you to read. He did not exaggerate.** He wiped out the record of the date of crossing the Jordan, interpolated the Shobak story, spoilt the entry on Alexander, spoilt the entry on the Exile, spoilt the entry on attacks by the ill-named Simon the Just and invented a second exile, replaced everything after Sejanus with rubbish up till the time of Zēnōn (except that the entry on Antoninus Pius only lost detail, and the description of Bāba's administration and the information on Dositheos and the Dosithean factions survived), deleted everything between Zēnōn and Muhammad, and wiped out part of the entry on Muhammad. Argument will be given further on that he cut out a lot of episodes even for the time before the first century A.D. He obscured the date of composition given by A.F.

Extent of damage

We can now define the extent of the damage to historical content. The original pericope about Alexander has been replaced by legends. The original pericope about the Exile has been replaced by a mixture of rubbish and isolated pieces of information. Attacks by the bizarrely named Simon the Just have been turned into a second exile in the late Persian period. It is said the Persians let the Jews attack the Samaritans to the extent of depopulating Samaria. There are more passages like this. On all these isolated single passages see the first pages of my article *Samaritan History, Fiction, and Bad Fantasy*. I think the Shobak story is an interpolation not only in the Arabic Joshua book but also in the work of A.F. These are all single pieces of damage in the first half of the book. It will be argued further on that a lot of episodes have been cut out. The whole of the last half of the book has been replaced by a massive amount of rubbish, page after page, with some sporadic isolated facts left. Everything after Sejanus till the end of the book has been spoilt, except for a few short passages. There is mostly fictionalised history and invention. The detailed information about Bāba's administration is intact, though in the wrong place. The information about the Dositheos and the Dosithean factions is intact nearly everywhere, though in the wrong place. The notice of Antonius Pius is intact, though probably simplified. The description of destruction of the sanctuary by the emperor Zēnōn is remarkably well preserved. Some invention shows up even here, however. For example, there are two versions of a grave being located by the emperor Zēnōn so as to stop the Samaritans from worshipping. The nefarious Simon is a Christian invention. A lot is gone altogether. Both Jewish revolts are gone. The wars after the time of Zēnōn are gone. All the oppression by means of legislation is gone, and replaced by made up stories of persecution at the wrong time.

An assessment like this is still not enough. The book as we have it is uneven. The original must have been much longer. There is careful detail about some events, while others are left out. Saul is prominent. The story about Amnon and his sister and then his brother is there in full detail. I suppose the falsifier thought the readers he was aiming at would like it. Boring administrative arrangements under David and Solomon affecting the north are left out. What is said about David in regard to recognition of the sacred place is self-contradictory. There is a cursory note about David having someone killed so he can get his hands on his wife,

but without names and with nothing said about Solomon. There are no Ammonites or Edomites or Phoenicians or Syrians. There is hardly anything about the history of the northern kingdom. There is no Maccabean revolt. There is no mention of Samaritans outside Palestine. The list of High Priests at the end of the book shows how a lot of names have been cut out in the inferior replacement. Stenhouse p. 243. That must have happened when pericopes were cut out.

Damage goes beyond loss of historical information. The chronology has been manipulated. Two years are lost at the time of the Flood, so that entry into Canaan is put two years too early. The figures have been changed in the list near the start of the book and again at the end. The falsifier insists on the alteration. See my article *Restoring the Traditional Linkage*, pp. 2 and 3. Reckoning of sabbatical years and Jubilee years is made impossible. To this day the Samaritans have no traditional knowledge of linkage of years of entry with years of Creation because of this falsifier. The calculation of dates has been manipulated by falsely saying the forty years of Bāba Rabba should not be counted. There is more. The title of the book by A.F. was lost because the falsifier needed to drop the title-page. This will be explained. Stenhouse and Crown and others think Kitāb at-Tārīkh “the book of the history” to be a title. No sensitivity. Words like this could not be a title. They are a label. Not all the manuscripts even have a label. No-one has noticed anything wrong. A.F. says he wrote in 756 A.H. (1355 A.D). The conversion to years of Creation given by him here has been wiped out. This will be explained. Now the Samaritans have no confidence in their knowledge of years of Creation.

The common practice of using the mess about Bāba Rabba to work a date out without any try at editorial criticism or source criticism or plain careful reading is not Wissenschaft. It is obvious on the face of it that the book ascribed to A.F. has been debased in places. The parts about Bāba are amongst the worst, though not the very worst. None of the claims for putting Bāba in one century or another have come from reading the way historians read. One example. No-one explained how the emperor Philip, who died in 249 A.D., is put in Christianised Constantinople. Ben-Ḥayyim and everyone else believed Christian Constantinople was right and forgot about the prominent mention of Philip. Stenhouse and Crown believed the real Philip was meant but did not explain how he got put in Christianised Constantinople.

The question of revisions by A.F.

It remains to consider how these findings fit in with the argument in my article *The Second Recension of the Work of Abu'l-Fateḥ* where it was proposed that A.F. revised some parts of his book. If the book as we have it in all the manuscripts has been extensively changed, all extant manuscripts must be descended from exemplars made by the falsifier. To the extent that they still represent the author's work, they can only show one form of it. Nevertheless, it is undeniable that there are at least two records of a philosophical debate between a Samaritan called Lībi and Alexander of Aphrodisias. See my article *The Second Recension*, p. 11, and Daiber's article. Daiber has proven that the long form quoted from A.F. in the *Comprehensive History* is authentic. It ends with an expression of satisfaction by A.F. that he has got it right at last. The form in the manuscripts of the work of A.F. ends with an expression of dissatisfaction by A.F. on his ability to follow the argument and an apology to the reader. Stenhouse p. 165. There are two intermediate forms, a slightly longer one in all manuscripts of the second recension of the work of A.F. except A, and one slightly longer still in A. Rather than positing

that there were three or four different records of three or four different tries by A.F., as I did in my article, it seems best to posit a second record by A.F. of a successful try, with the full form being quoted in the Comprehensive History, and with expansions of the original record against the record of the successful try in the second recension of the work of A.F. and ms. A. It is known that the scribe of ms. A and the author of the Comprehensive History independently used collections of superior readings garnered from fragments in the geniza before they were sold to Firkovitch. See my article *The Second Recension*. A fuller form of the record might have come into the second recension at the same time. There are known instances of superior readings appearing in the manuscripts of the second recension at this time. Notwithstanding all this, it is still not disproven that the version in the manuscripts comes from the falsifier, that the expression of dissatisfaction is his, and that the expression of satisfaction at the end of the complete version quoted in the Comprehensive History is his.

On closer examination, one of the examples of readings that might be from another recension that I quoted can be discarded. In my article *The Second Recension* on p. 8 I quoted two readings that had been restored, one that had been restored in ms. A and the Hebrew translation, and one that had been restored by Khadr in the Comprehensive History. One reading is “They would not put food out for cattle on the day of the sabbath”. The other is “They would not observe a Festival except on the sabbath, even if it had to be moved from its time to another time”. I thought this was an example of rewriting by the author, but was wrong. I should have taken more notice of the implications of the defective reading “They would not put a day” in all other manuscripts. This must be one of the places where all text-witnesses go back to tries at reading a smudged or faded exemplar. See my article, pp. 13 to 14. On one try, one set of words has been recovered, and on another try, another set. There are two more readings that might be survivals of different wording by the author. See my article, p. 11. There is the reading “The experts did not approve him” in ms. A instead of “The townspeople did not approve him” at 157:3 – 4, in reference to Dositheos. This difference in wording expresses a substantially different view of congregational organisation. The other possibility is the reading “They said the dead would soon rise by miraculous divine favour *karāmatan* to Lībi and his community as children of Dositheos the Prophet of God” in ms. A instead of “They said the dead would rise soon as children of Dositheos the Prophet of God” at 156:14 – 15. There is a substantial addition of theological content in the version in ms. A. Both of the readings just mentioned are in the notice of Dositheos. It has been suggested in this article and previous articles that the material on Dositheos and the Dosithean factions was copied as a separate pamphlet at one stage, perhaps with the fiction about Simon in the middle. In the present state of knowledge, there is no way of going further into the implications of this proposal. Notwithstanding all this, the phenomena of the two pairs of readings in two different places just quoted could be explained by supposing that in each case what is in most of the manuscripts comes from the falsifier and what is in ms. A comes from the hand of A.F. The material on Dositheos could still have been in a separate pamphlet at some stage.

The date of the low-grade abridgment and low-grade partial rewriting

It has been remarked a few times that the wording of the seven or so stories attached at the end of the Arabic Joshua book is not the same as the wording of the same stories as they stand in the manuscripts of the work of A.F. There are three possible explanations. First

possibility. They are a booklet of bad adaptations of pericopes from an old history. They resemble pericopes in the work of A.F. because he knew the history book from which the inferior adaptations had been made. Second possibility. They are a booklet of bad adaptations of pericopes from a history book. Someone adapted some pericopes in the work of A.F. using the method in the earlier bad adaptations and largely copying them. The same person changed the calculation of the date of entry into Canaan to agree with the Arabic Joshua book using the same argument about dropping two years at the time of the Flood. Third possibility. They are a booklet of bad adaptations of pericopes in lost histories. Later on the same person rewrote the same pericopes and put them within the work of A.F., replacing what had been there. All extant manuscripts of the work of A.F. are descended from a manuscript with some pericopes replaced this way. The first possibility can easily be discarded. The corresponding pericopes in the manuscripts of the work of A.F. are bad. They could not come from the hand of A.F. Even the best of them are below his standard. The one about Alexander, for example, leaves out the record of his irrevocable endowment of the sacred place on Mt. Gerizim. See my book, p. 109. The bad ones are not only below the standard of the work of A.F., but below any acceptable standard. Hadrian is fused with Vespasian. The writer of the account of the Exile has not heard of Assyrians or Babylonians. He has not heard of the northern and southern kingdoms, under the names of Israel and Judah or any other names. The second possibility is implausible in the form just stated. It is made more implausible by the evidence of much more extensive damage throughout the book. The third possibility is neat. It turns out to be workable. It is better than workable if you look closely. The falsifier left a lot of traces. I think it was on purpose, and he thought no-one would read the signs left because no-one was as clever as him.

Timing is not a difficulty. The extant form of the Arabic Joshua book is not later than 1360 A.D. Juynboll dates the original part of the Leiden manuscript, designated S by me, to 1362/63. The original part breaks off in the middle of ch. 46, the story about Alexander. The rest can be assumed to be from the same time. The manuscript designated L by me is not later than 1360. See my article *The Transmission of the Samaritan Joshua-Judges*, p. 26. Ch. 47, the story about Hadrian fused with Vespasian, is only in S. All other manuscripts have the story about the High Priest's daughter.

The date of 756 A.H., or 1355 A.D., for the work of A.F. is given twice in the book, in the foreword and at the end. In the second place a conversion to years of Creation is given. The figure is wrong and could not come from A.F. See my book of 2024, p. 160. In that place I assumed a blunder by a scribe. I was wrong. This is the work of the falsifier, deliberately causing confusion about the date of his work to make it get confused with the real book. Notice that he quotes A.F. speaking in the first person in the authentic foreword, and says nothing to tell the reader that the book he is looking at is not what it seems to be. In the very last lines of the book he quotes the date 756 A.H. from A.F. and adds that this is after the passage of 5,803 years from Creation. (This date is only preserved in ms. C, which is the oldest for this part of the book. All later manuscripts have an attempt at correction). The correspondence given is obviously wrong at first sight. The correct correspondence is after the passage of 5,780 years. Anyone would think a scribe had ignorantly changed the year of Creation to the year that he was writing, 23 years after the book was composed. This is what I thought myself up till now. No. It was 23 years after the book was composed, in 5804 A.M. (sic) or 1378 or early 1379 A.D., that the falsifier published his work. He thinks he is smart. He keeps the name of A.F. at

the start of the book by quoting what A.F. says about his work, but does not write the title of the book with the author's name against it. He does not give a title-page. This is why the name of the book was lost. He speaks in the first person twice near the end. (Vilmar 178:11 and 13. Stenhouse bottom of p. 248 and top of p. 249). He does not name himself. He copies the date of 756 A.H. from A.F. but gives the date of his own destructiveness in years of Creation. He speaks in the first person again right at the end. See above, p. 7 top. Even then the reader would have to already be suspicious to take the meaning in. Even then, the reader would not know how much had been cut out or changed. Then he can say he said he was not A.F. and said he was writing twenty-three years later **when A.F. had died at last** and it isn't his fault if no-one understood because they weren't as clever as him. This is while pocketing a lot of money selling a book cheaper than the real work of A.F. because much shorter which sold well because people thought it was the work of A.F., but he never wrote a title-page making any false claim and never said he copied the whole book and people don't read properly. And he did compile the seven pericopes at the end of the Arabic Joshua book that he copied into the work of A.F. years later and deserves something for that. And he did rewrite some pericopes about boring stuff, tax and building permits and so on, and now they are all entertaining with dogs more powerful than lions and wicked guardians and stuff. And actually he did so much work on the original book that he is the author of a new edition. Anyway, the author's relatives and friends have died too by now and any younger ones are conveniently up there in Tyre. Some partial vindication of the author has been done in this article nearly exactly six and a half centuries later by showing where the faults in the extant replacement of his book come from.

Some conclusions on how to read

In the parts that have been damaged, everything has to be looked at critically. There needs to be constant attention to pick up what might have been rewritten for readers not interested in real information. A prize example is the record of a new regulation of needing to get official permission to put up a new synagogue on top of the normal requirement of lodging plans to get approval for any building, a record that is hidden in the story about the synagogue put up by Iqbon. Another prize example is the record of how Hyrcanus bolstered his rule over Samaria in a way cheaper than using force by sending royal offerings and gifts to the sanctuary on Mt. Gerizim, while being careful not to give anyone the chance to accuse him of officiating as a Priest there. The falsifier said he came to accept that Mt. Gerizim was the true sacred place and sent offerings in his private capacity but the Samaritans still did not let him go there. See my book, p. 110. The falsifier had a method of working that often lets hints of what was originally there get through. It was less effort to rewrite what was there than invent from scratch. See my article *Roman Policy towards Samaritans in the Second Century A.D.*, p. 9. Nothing can be dismissed out of hand. On the other hand, a lot must be dismissed. It is like trying to use the *Historia Augusta*. Worse. It follows that the parts that are damaged must be delineated well. That has largely been done in this article but much more work is needed.

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